

Unraveling spinal cord injury caregiver burden in Indonesia

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Article Info

Article history:

Received Dec 19, 2023

Revised Mar 15, 2024

Accepted Apr 24, 2024

Keywords:

Burden
Caregivers
Indonesia
Quality of life
Spinal cord injuries

ABSTRACT

Diverse cultural, social, and economic backgrounds significantly influence the caregiver burden of spinal cord injury (SCI) patients, affecting their quality of life (QoL) and the overall care experience. This study was done to identify spinal cord caregivers' QoL in Indonesia through their burden and the variables that influence it. A cross-sectional study was conducted at Dr. Hasan Sadikin Hospital, Bandung, Indonesia, involved 137 primary SCI caregivers. The burden of these caregivers was evaluated using the Indonesian version of the Zarit Burden Interview (ZBI) and the World Health Organization Quality of Life-BREF questionnaires. The data was analyzed with multiple linear regression and spearman analysis using SPSS version 24. The majority of SCI caregivers have a mild to moderate burden (54.7%). The burden score was significantly correlated, especially with occupational status and the length of interaction each day ($p < 0.001$). It also found a significant with strong negative correlation (referring to the Guilford criteria) between caregiver burden and QoL (r -value -0.750 ; p -value < 0.001). Indonesian caregivers' cultural and economic backgrounds may alleviate their burden in caregiving, but attention to patient occupational status and care duration is crucial to prevent worsening their quality of life, particularly for SCI survivors they care for.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Spinal cord injuries (SCI) cause loss of motor, sensory, and autonomic functions, resulting in disability and life-threatening consequences [1]. Epidemiological data on SCI in Indonesia and its disability are not yet available nationally; however, there are only two study about SCI epidemiology data. The recent study in 2021 showed there were 126 cases, of which 85 cases were traumatic SCI, and 41 were non-traumatic SCI in Dr. Soetomo General Hospital Surabaya [2]. The disability associated with SCI will cause dependence on others, so it will take at least one caregiver to accompany the patient and provide primary care [3]. Studies have shown that primary caregivers of individuals with SCI have some level of caregiver burden [4], [5]. The high burden of caring significantly affects the caregiver's physical and emotional well-being and is associated with a lower quality of life (QoL) [5]. There is an urgent need for focused interventions and support networks to counteract these negative impacts. Caregiver QoL is essential because it may impact the care they provide [6]. The burden on caregivers of individuals with SCI can be influenced by several factors, including the patient's and caregiver's characteristics, and it tends to be country-specific, determined by socio-economic, geographical, and cultural values [7], [8].

As the fourth most populated country in the world and the biggest archipelago, Indonesia is home to a diverse range of ethnicities and cultures, making it difficult for residents to receive equal healthcare [9]. This dilemma impacts many areas of healthcare, most notably on how SCI survivors are managed during their rehabilitation. Facilities with specialized rehabilitation units are still hard to come by in Indonesia. Only two hospitals provide SCI services, and they are located on Java Island in the provinces of Jakarta and Central Java. Although general rehabilitation services can be provided in many different hospitals, the difficulty for SCI rehabilitation is worsened by the lack of skilled personnel. Transportation-related obstacles further impair the situation by making it more difficult for patients to go from home to the hospital [10]. Because of this, a large number of SCI survivors are required to receive their care at home from their relatives. Primary carers, which are frequently family members, are unpaid informal carers who live with the patient and provide care [4]. However, Indonesia is among numerous Asian countries whose traditions value caring for family members as a sign of respect and honor [11]. Most carers are psychologically and emotionally inadequate to perform demanding and complex care obligations because they lack the proper knowledge and training, which might result in the increase of the carer's load [4]. The shortage of thorough epidemiological data about the caregiver burden in Indonesia highlights a crucial knowledge gap regarding the complete range of difficulties informal caregivers face. This scarcity prevents the creation of the focused treatments and support networks required to successfully reduce the strain on carers. Given the significance of reliable epidemiological data in shaping healthcare policy and allocating resources, filling this knowledge vacuum is essential in improving the health of Indonesian carers and care users.

It is critical to identify factors influencing caregiver burden in Indonesia so that appropriate action can be taken to address them. This study intends to analyze caregiver burden and its correlation with the QoL of caregivers and determine the factors that influence them. The communal nature of Indonesian society holds family members to a high standard of care and commitment throughout life, which could overburden the family as caregivers [12]. We hypothesized that the occupational status of individuals with SCI, SCI level, SCI duration, health insurance ownership, the caregiver's education level, the duration of care, and the length of interaction each day would be associated with caregiver burden in Indonesia.

The strong sense of community in Indonesian society, which holds family members to a high standard of care and commitment throughout life, could lead to an overburdening of the family as caregivers. We conduct this study because it is crucial to conduct research on caregivers in Indonesia, as understanding the factors that influence caregiver burden can help develop effective strategies to reduce the burden, thereby improving the quality of life of caregivers which has never conducted before [13]. The caregiver burden and QoL showed a statistically significant and substantial negative correlation. A high caregiver burden can have negative impacts on physical, emotional, mental health, and social life, which lowers the QoL of the caregiver [3], [5], [13], [14]. The condition of family caregiving is one example of how cultures are a sort of intergenerational inheritance that actively impacts people's lives [15]. Research on family carers particularly Indonesia, is essentially required because by recognizing the factors that can influence the caregiver burden, a proper approach to reduce the burden will improve caregiver QoL that also its impact to QoL of SCI patient.

2. METHOD

This study adopted a cross-sectional analytic design. The population of this study included the primary caregivers of SCI patients at the physical medicine and rehabilitation department, Dr. Hasan Sadikin Hospital, Bandung, Indonesia, from June to August 2021. A consecutive sampling procedure was used to select the study participants. A sample size of at least 137 participants was needed to achieve a significance level of 0.05, a power of 0.8, and a 95% confidence interval. The study was approved by the Research Ethics Committee of Dr. Hasan Sadikin Hospital (number: LB.02.01/X.6.5/137/2021) and received research permission from the hospital. All participants provided written informed consent prior to data collection.

The study's inclusion criteria were as follows: primary caregivers of SCI individuals over the age of 18 years, caring for SCI individuals for at least four hours per day for at least three consecutive months, having a minimum primary school education, agreeing to participate in the study, and providing written informed consent. Participants who had a cognitive issue (Montreal cognitive assessment-indonesian version score <26) and were unable to communicate in Indonesian were excluded.

The sociodemographic data were divided into two categories: individuals with SCI and caregivers. Sex, age, education level, marital status, occupation, health insurance ownership, SCI level, American Spinal Injury Association (ASIA) impairment scale classification, the etiology of SCI, and the duration of SCI were among the sociodemographic and clinical factors examined in individuals with SCI. The caregivers' sociodemographic factors included sex, age, education level, marital status, occupation, and relationship with the individuals with SCI, the duration of care, and interaction duration in a day.

The Indonesian version of the Zarit Burden Interview (ZBI), which had been translated, validated, and shown to have good reliability for assessing caregiver burden, was used to assess the caregiver burden [14].

There are 22 questions with a total score of 88. Each item receives a score between 0 and 4, with the options being: never (0), infrequently (1), occasionally (2), rather frequently (3), and almost always (4). The overall scores of the individuals were divided into four groups, each representing a distinct level of burden severity. "little or no burden" was defined as a score between 0–20, "mild-to-moderate burden" was defined as a score between 21–40, "moderate-to-severe burden" defined as a score between the number 41-60, and "very severe burden" was defined as a score between 61–88 [16].

The caregivers' QoL was assessed using the Indonesian version of the World Health Organization (WHO) QoL-BREF (WHOQoL-BREF) questionnaire, which had been determined to be a valid and reliable questionnaire [15], [16]. The WHOQoL-BREF questionnaire has 26 items to measure quality of life through four domains: physical, psychological, social, and environmental. A Likert scale of 1 to 5 is used to score each item, with 1 indicating "very dissatisfied" and 5 indicating "very satisfied". The scores are classified into: "very poor" (0-20), "poor" (21-40), "average" (41-60), "good" (61-80), and "very good" (81-100) [15], [16].

Numerical variables were reported using means and standard deviations, whereas frequencies and percentages were used to report descriptive statistics for categorical variables. Using multiple linear regression analysis, these characteristics were correlated with caregiver burden levels. The association between caregiver burden and caregiver QoL was analyzed using a rank correlation analysis (Spearman's rho). The statistical significance level was set at $p < 0.05$. SPSS ver. 24, was used for all data analyses.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Results

The characteristics of the subject were showed as in Table 1 with most caregivers having mild-to-moderate burden. The caregiver burden score, assessed using the ZBI, showed a mean score of 35.98 ± 13.26 , with most of the caregivers having mild to moderate burdens as illustrated in Table 1 and having moderate QoL, which has an average of 50.45 ± 8.62 as detailed in Table 2. Table 3 shows the patient's occupation, level of injury, duration of SCI, ownership of health insurance, caregiver education level, duration of care, and length of interaction per day as a whole had a statistically significant effect on caregiver burden scores.

To see the effect of each variable examined in this study on the caregiver burden score partially, the t-test was used with the results as shown in Table 4. Statistical analysis, as shown in Table 4, showed that the occupational status of individuals with SCI and the interaction length per day were found to have a significant effect on the caregiver burden ($p < 0.05$). The findings indicate that the burden on caregivers and employment status increases as the duration of daily interaction increases. Additionally, the lack of occupation among individuals with SCI will further heighten the burden on caregivers. Other variables such as the severity of injury, duration of SCI, presence of health insurance, caregiver's level of education, and length of caregiving had no significant correlation with caregiver burden. Based on Spearman's statistical analysis, it also found a significant, strong negative correlation (referring to the Guilford criteria) between caregiver burden and QoL (r-value -0.750 ; $p < 0.001$) as illustrated in Table 5. It shows that a caregiver's quality of life would decline with increasing caregiving burden.

3.2. Discussion

This study showed that most SCI caregivers experience a mild to moderate burden. It may be influenced by Indonesian culture, which believes caring for the infirm members of the family is considered an obligation and is also consistent with religious values [17], [18]. Inherent family values, such as commitment, solidarity, protection, and concern for others, are cultural factors. However, in many cultures, especially in nations with patriarchal cultures like Indonesia, these social standards are detrimental to women. Caring duties have a profound impact on caregivers' quality of life. Caregivers, in particular, frequently encounter physical and health-related challenges, resulting in a reduction in their perceived quality of life [19], [20]. The workload and responsibilities of women in the home cause various issues, including familial conflict, financial stress, and a decline in the health of female caregivers. The stress that comes with caring for others also impacts women's mental health [21]. These characteristics may alter for family caregivers in developed countries, where education levels are higher, access to healthcare facilities is better, and a preference for professional caregivers exists. In Western countries, caring for a family is not a cultural norm [22].

In research by Sinha *et al.* [7], the majority of participants indicated a moderate-to-severe load. This could be due to a higher interaction duration each day (>12 h) than reported in this study, and the value of taking care of the family is a natural condition in Indonesia. Close relationships among extended family members in Indonesia may reduce the stress on caretakers [23]. Other research has found that the main domain of caregiver burden in affluent countries is time-dependent [3], [24]. The duration of daily engagement between caregivers and people with SCI had a substantial impact on caregiver burden. The majority of caretakers were in their productive years, with a mean age of 40.7 ± 11.2 years. By providing

long-term care, even lifelong assistance might interfere with the caregiver's daily activities and lifestyle, increasing multiple responsibilities conflict, limiting their social activities, and increasing their load [25], [26]. The caregiver's burden grows in proportion to the amount of time spent providing care [7].

Table 1. Characteristics of individuals with spinal cord injury and caregivers

Characteristics		SCI individuals (n=137)	Caregivers (n=137)
Gender, n (%)	Male	66 (48.2)	43 (31.4)
	Female	71 (51.8)	94 (68.6)
Age (years), mean (SD), range		43.7 (14.6), 19-69	40.7 (11.2), 21-67
Occupation, n (%)	Working	39 (28.5)	47 (34.3)
	Not working	98 (71.5)	90 (65.7)
Education, n (%)	Elementary school	16 (11.7)	7 (5.1)
	Junior high school	38 (27.7)	45 (32.8)
	Senior high school	81 (59.1)	84 (61.3)
	Bachelor/Diploma	2 (1.5)	1 (0.7)
Marital status, n (%)	Married	116 (84.7)	130 (94.9)
	Single	19 (13.9)	8 (5.1)
	Widow/widower	2 (1.5)	0 (0)
Health insurance, n (%)	Has health insurance	137 (100)	
	No health insurance	0 (0)	
Level of injury, n (%)	Paraplegic	121 (88.3)	
	Tetraplegic	16 (11.7)	
ASIA classification, n (%)	AIS A	35 (25.5)	
	AIS B	14 (10.2)	
	AIS C	34 (24.8)	
	AIS D	53 (38.7)	
	AIS ND (not determined)	1 (0.7)	
Etiology, n (%)	Traumatic	38 (27.7)	
	Nontraumatic	99 (72.3)	
Duration of SCI (months), mean (SD), range		13.4 (8.4), 3-60	
Relationship status, n (%)	Parent		20 (14.6)
	Child		28 (20.4)
	Sibling		2 (1.5)
	Spouse		86 (62.8)
	Other		1 (0.7)
Caregiving duration (months), mean (SD), range			13.4 (8.3), 3-60
Interaction duration in a day (h), mean (SD), range			7.7 (2.8), 4-20
Caregiver burden score	Median		34
	Range		17-62
Caregiver burden classification, n (%)	Little or no burden		(6.6)
	Mild to moderate		75 (54.7)
	Moderate to severe		49 (35.8)
	Severe		4 (2.9)

American spinal injury association (ASIA); American spinal injury association impairment scale classification (AIS); spinal cord injury (SCI); Zarit Burden Interview (ZBI).

Table 2. Quality of life score in caregivers

Variable	Mean (SD)	Median	Range
Caregiver quality of life score (WHOQoL-BREF)	50.45 (8.62)	49	35-71

WHOQoL-BREF, World Health Organization Quality of Life-BRIEF

Table 3. The effect of independent variables to caregiver burden

	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Regression	12035.90	7.00	1719.41	18.66	<0.001
Residual	11889.03	129.00	92.16		
Total	23924.93	136.00			

Note: df, degree of freedom; F, F ratio; Sig, significance.

Table 4. Linear regression analysis of factors influencing caregiver burden score

Variable	Caregiver burden score		
	Regression coefficients	SE	p-value
Occupational status of SCI individuals	-4.445	2.157	0.041*
Level of injury	2.919	2.660	0.275
Duration of SCI (months)	-0.878	0.901	0.332
Health insurance	2.915	1.952	0.138
Education of caregiver	0.464	1.423	0.745
Caregiving duration (months)	1.477	0.910	0.107
Interaction duration in a day (hours)	2.618	0.320	<0.01*

Note: *p-value <0.05: statistically significant standard error (SE).

Table 5. Correlation analysis between caregiver burden score and caregiver quality of life score

Variable	Correlation	r	p-value
Correlation between caregiver burden score and caregiver quality of life score	Spearman	-0.750	< 0.001*

Note: *p-value <0.05: statistically significant; r: correlation coefficient.

The financial burden is increasing, which may be caused by the Indonesian health system itself. The system now consists of public and private providers and financing [27], [28]. The only study about this system showed that the government share of total health expenditure also remains low, at only 39%, whereas private, primarily out-of-pocket expenditure, is 60%. The Indonesian government has implemented different health-care social insurance systems, although the emphasis is on curative care services and health infrastructure that supports medical care [29], [30]. This means that caring for SCI patients at home needs other economic support sources. Even if rehabilitation services are covered by social insurance, transportation to distant health facilities causes other financial burdens for the caregiver [31], [32], [33]. This study showed that health insurance had no statistically significant effect on caregiver burden scores. This might be because caregivers should still fund the additional costs associated with providing care, such as transportation, over-the-counter medications, and medical equipment that is not covered by health insurance [34]. To fulfill their numerous complex tasks, caregivers in Indonesia require support. These involve planning and providing hands-on care, keeping track of and managing symptoms, providing emotional support, taking care of and interacting with the larger family, accessing resources and managing finances, acting as the patient's advocate, navigating the healthcare system, as well as preparing for an uncertain future [35].

The limitations of this study were that it was conducted within a small group at one location; therefore, the study's results could not be applied to the overall population in Indonesia. Furthermore, we did not consider other factors predicted to affect the caregiver burden, such as medical rehabilitation programs; the caregiver's knowledge, skills, health problems, and coping mechanisms; social support; and kinship relationships with individuals with SCI. As a result, more research into the association between these variables and caregiver load is required.

4. CONCLUSION

The caregiver burden can be influenced by some factors. This study showed the occupational status of individuals with SCI and the duration of interaction per day had significant effects on caregiver burden. Interventions to manage these two aspects may help ease caregiver burden. There was also a substantial and significant correlation between the QoL of the caregivers of individuals with SCI and the burden of caregiving. Caregiver QoL may have an impact on the care they provide as well as the well-being of individuals with SCI. The results of this study can be used as the foundation for policies and strategies for improving the QoL of individuals with SCI.

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